

Technologies for ocean sensing (TechOceanS project).

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To address oceanographic community requirements for autonomous observations, new types of technology must be developed. New in-situ sensors and samplers will have to measure new parameters, reduce in size and power consumption, increase measurement traceability, improve stability, reduce mechanical engineering requirements and improve communication and automatic data transfer to data centres. TechOceanS project will fill the existing gaps by delivering sensors, samplers and improved image processing workflows capable of remotely measuring essential ocean variables (EOVs) as well as regulatory targets such as the Marine Strategy Framework Directive and OSPAR. To test the technology, a set of experiments and integration on a suit of platforms have been organised. The final tests were carried out in Gran Canaria in spring 2024 where 7 new technologies developed in this project were combined and integrated in 4 different autonomous vehicles and deployed in Taliarte harbour. This unique opportunity was used to provide a multidisciplinary practical training with students and included students and technicians from ODA recipient states.

In alignment with the objective of the UN Ocean Decade to secure “a transparent and accessible ocean”, TechOceanS has joined a growing partnership of initiatives and has a repository of methodological documents and candidate best practices in both the Ocean Best Practices System (OBPS) and Better Biomolecular Ocean Protocols (BeBOP). These protocols are followed during sensor tests and are available for a community review in these platforms alongside sensor development templates developed in the project.

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